

Chemistry of Terminalia Species. Part VIII*. Partial Synthesis of Arjunolic Acid

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By the action of lead tetra-acetate, methyl hederagenate has been converted into the corresponding 2-acetoxy derivative. The latter has been reduced with NaBH_4 ; subsequent deacetylation with alkali provides methyl arjunolate. This is regarded as a partial synthesis of arjunolic acid. The synthesis has also been repeated with hederagenin-18(α)-lactone to afford 2,23-diacetoxy-3-keto-arjunolic lactone.

2 α , 3 β , 23-Trihydroxy system has been established in arjunolic acid¹, baringtogenol², tomentosic acid³, and terminolic acid⁴. Bassic acid has also a hydroxyl group at 2-position in addition to 3 β , 23-dihydroxy system, but its steric configuration has been recently shown to be β^3 . The 2,3-dihydroxy system is, however, not so frequent among triterpenoids. Maslinic acid⁵, 2 α ,3 β -olean-12-en-28-oic acid, is a lone representative isolated from the husks of *Olea europaea*. In tetracyclic triterpenes, 2 α -hydroxy-3-keto-grouping, is, however, characteristic of cucurbitacins⁷. Experiments leading to the hydroxylation of the second position may therefore be of synthetic significance.

Hederagenin (I: R=H) from Indian soap nuts (*Sapindus emarginatus*) was the starting material for the synthesis of arjunolic acid (IV: R=H). Methyl hederagenate (II: R=Me), obtained by oxidation of methyl hederagenin (I: R=Me) with permanganate in acetone⁸, has a fairly active α -methylene group at 2-position. Lead tetra-acetate is the reagent of our choice. This reagent⁹⁻¹⁰ is well known to give rise to α -acetoxy-ketonic compounds and has been used frequently for this purpose with a variety of compounds. By the action of lead tetra-acetate on methyl hederagenate (II: R=Me) in glacial acetic acid, 2-acetoxy-3-oxo-23-hydroxy-olean-12-en-28-oate was obtained which was reduced with sodium borohydride. Deacetylation of the product gave rise to a compound which on careful purification afforded methyl arjunolate (IV: R=Me), identical in every respect with an authentic sample of methyl arjunolate.

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1. King *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3995, 2985.
2. Anantaraman and Pillai, *ibid.*, 1956, 4369.
3. Row and Rao, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 827.
4. King and King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4469.
5. King and Yardley, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 393.
6. Caglioti *et al.*, *Gazzetta*, 1961, **91**, 1387.
7. Lavis *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, **22**, 23.
8. Jacobs, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1925, **63**, 621.
9. Rosenkronz *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 145.
10. Chowdhry *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2725.

The success of this procedure was further substantiated with 3-keto-23-hydroxy-clean-18(α)-lactone (VI) which was obtained by the permanganate oxidation of hederagenin-18(α)-lactone (V). The former gave 2-acetoxy-3-keto-lactone (VII) with lead tetra-acetate in good yield, the acetyl derivative of which is identical in every respect with 2,23-diacetoxy-3-keto-arjunolic-18(α)-lactone (VIII), prepared according to the method of King *et al.*¹¹ from arjunolic acid.

The correctness of the structures for the ketonic compounds (III and VII) is established by conversion to the diosphenols. The new diosphenols exhibit a green ferric coloration, different from that obtained from methyl hederagonate (II: R=Me) which shows brown ferric coloration¹¹. Lead tetra-acetate was originally felt to be a specific acetoxyating reagent. But recent instances are known in which lead tetra-acetate is partially stereospecific¹⁰. In the present instance, the 2 α -acetoxy compound (III: R=Me) was secured in 40% yield. A small quantity (30 mg.) of the 2 β -acetoxy isomer (IIIa) was also isolated. Further work on this compound was not pursued due to paucity of the yield.

11. Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 1185.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Hederagenin from Soap Nuts (Sapindus emarginatus).—The soap nut peels (1 kg.) were extracted thrice with hot ethanol (3×21). Removal of the solvent from the extract and addition of ether (800 ml) deposited a semisolid which resisted crystallisation. It was hydrolysed with 2*N* methanolic H_2SO_4 by refluxing for 5 hours and then extracted with ether. The ether extract was separated through alkali into an acid which was crystallised from acetone (charcoal) as colorless needles (5 g.), m.p. $319-21^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +66^\circ$ (c, 1.25 in ethanol). (Found: C, 76.28; H, 10.48. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_4$: C, 76.27; H, 10.17%). Dutts¹² recorded m.p. $327-29^\circ$ for hederagenin.

Methylhederagenin.—Hederagenin (5 g.) in methanol was treated with ethereal diazomethane. Working up in the usual way, the methyl ester crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. $238-40^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +70^\circ$ (c, 1.5 in $CHCl_3$).

Oxidation of Methylhederagenin.—Methylhederagenin was treated with excess of $KMnO_4$ in acetone (30 ml) and heated under reflux for 2 hours. The manganous salts were filtered and the clear filtrate, on removal of the solvent and crystallisation from methanol, deposited cubes of methyl hederagonate, m.p. $217-18^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +95^\circ$. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 9.85. $C_{31}H_{48}O_4$ requires C, 76.86; H, 9.92%).

Acetoxylation of Methyl Hederagonate: Methyl 2- α -Acetoxy-3-oxo-23-hydroxy-olean-12-en-28-oate.—Methyl hederagonate (2 g.), lead tetra-acetate (4 g.), and acetic acid (25 ml) were heated on a steam bath at 100° for 4 hrs. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was poured into water (100 ml). It was then extracted with ether, washed with aqueous sodium carbonate, and dried. Removal of the solvent deposited a glassy mass which was taken in benzene and purified through chromatography on alumina (30 g.). Elution with light petroleum-benzene (7:3, 200 ml) and crystallisation from ether-methanol (3:1) deposited colorless needles of methyl 2- α -acetoxy-3-oxo-23-hydroxy-olean-12-en-28-oate (0.8 g.), m.p. $168-70^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +50^\circ$ (c, 1.8 in $CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 72.96; H, 9.5. $C_{33}H_{50}O_6$ requires C, 73.04; H, 9.23%).

Methyl Arjunolate.—The preceding ester (0.5 g.) in methanol was treated with excess of sodium borohydride (1 g.) and left overnight. It was then diluted, acidified with H_2SO_4 and extracted with ether. Removal of the solvent deposited methyl acetyl arjunolate as a brown residue which resisted crystallisation.

The above acetyl ester was hydrolysed with 2*N* methanolic KOH. Working up in the usual way and purification through alumina, followed by crystallisation from methanol—ether (1:3), methyl arjunolate came out as fine needles (0.2 g.), melting alone or mixed with an authentic sample at $214-15^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +68^\circ$ (c, 1.2 in $CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 73.86; H, 10.22. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 74.10; H, 9.96%).

It formed the lactone triacetate, m.p. $265-66^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +18^\circ$ with 50% HBr-acetic acid. Its m.p. was undepressed by an authentic specimen.

18- α -Hederagenin lactone was prepared by the action of HBr—acetic acid on methylhederagenin. It was crystallised from methanol as flakes, m.p. 352° ; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +12^\circ$ (c, 1.5 in $CHCl_3$).

12. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 685.

3-Oxo-23-hydroxy-olean-18- α -lactone.—The preceding lactone (2.5 g.) in dry acetone (30 ml) was oxidised with KMnO_4 (2.5 g) in acetone for 2 hours, as in methylhederagenin. The product (1.4 g.) was worked up in the usual way and crystallised from methanol as stout prisms, m.p. 305-307°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 38^\circ$ (c, 2.2 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 76.27; H, 10.12. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 76.60; H, 9.78%).

2- α -Acetoxy-3-oxo-23-hydroxy-olean-18- α -lactone.—The preceding α -lactone (0.80 g.), lead tetra-acetate (1.0 g.), and acetic acid (10 ml) were heated on a steam-bath for 4 hours at 100°. The solvent was removed and the residue was poured into water (100 ml). The solid was filtered, dried, and acetylated directly with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Working up in the usual way and crystallisation from methanol deposited the 3-oxo-olean-18- α -lactone-2,23-diacetate as needles (150 mg.), m.p. 256-58°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 30^\circ$ (c, 0.8 in CHCl_3). Its m.p. remained undepressed with the authentic sample obtained by oxidation of arjunolic lactone 2,23-diacetate. (Found: C, 71.82; H, 9.32. Calc. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_7$: C, 71.58; H, 8.77%).

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